

الدولة الزيانية

By Elhadi Bououchma, Faculté des sciences humaines et sociales - Université de Tamanghasset

Entry tags: Arabic, Religious Group (fr), سنية مالكية, Language, مجموعة سنية

الزيانيون و بنو زيان و عبد الواديون و بنو عبد الوادي أو الوادي هي أسماء متعددة لمعنى واحد يخص بنو زيان بتلمسان، يعود نسبهم إلى قبيلة بنو عبد الوادي، الذين هم أحد فروع قبيلة زناتة البربرية التي كانت حياتها تقوم على البداوة والترحال، امتدت مواطنهم من تيهرت شرقا إلى وادي ملوية غربا. بالنسبة لأصل التسمية بالزيانيون فإنها ترجع إلى لجدهم عن أبيهم زيان بن ثابت بن محمد بن بن قاسم بن محمد. عاش الزيانيون تحت حكم الدولة الموحدية وكانوا الحامين لهذه الدولة في هذه الجهة وفي أواخرها استقروا بتلمسان وفي جواراتها وأقاموا تحصينات كبيرة بها وأصبحت عاصمة لهم بالنسبة لعمر دولة بنو زيان فقد امتدت بين 1235-1554م

Date Range: 1235 CE - 1554 CE

Region: الدولة الزيانية

Region tags: Algeria, الدولة الزيانية, تلمسان

عمرت الدولة الزيانية أو ما عرف بدولة بنو عبد الوادي بين 1234 و1554م بمعنى ان هذه الدولة عاشت حوالي 3 قرون ، مؤسسها هو يغمراسن بن زيان، عرفت عدة حكام منهم 7 حكام وأمرأ بارزين منهم: 1- يغمراسن بن زيان بين 1236 و1283- 2- أبو سعيد عثمان بن يغمراسن بين 1283 و1303. 3- أبو حمو موسى الأول بين 1308 و1318م. 4- عبد الرحمن ابن تاشفين بين 1318 و1337م. 5- أبو سعيد وابو ثابت بين 1348 و1354- 6- أبو حمو موسى الثاني بين 1359 و1389م 7- أبي عبد الله محمد المتوكل بين 1442 و1468م

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: مختار حساني، تاريخ الدولة الزيانية، ج1، الأحوال السياسية، منشورات الحضارة، الجزائر، ط1، 2009، ص290
- Source 2: مختار حساني، تاريخ الدولة الزيانية، ج2، الأحوال السياسية، منشورات الحضارة، الجزائر، ط1، 2009، ص331
- Source 3: خالد بلعربي، الدولة الزيانية في عهد يغمراسن: دراسة تاريخية وحضارية 633 هـ - 681 هـ / 1235 م - 1282 م، منشورات المنهل، 2011، ص373

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.iasj.net/iasj/download/404455dd6dfa57e0>
- Source 1 Description: فتن كامل شاهين، دولة بنو عبد الوادي (بنو زيان): دراسة تاريخية
- Source 2 URL: https://www.univ-chlef.dz/ratsh/la_revue_N_19/Article_Revue_Academique_N_19_2018/Science_social/Article_9.pdf
- Source 2 Description: هادي جلول، الحركة العلمية في حضرة تلمسان وعناية السلطة الزيانية بها (ق 8- 9/ 14 - 15 م)
- Source 3 URL: https://journals.ekb.eg/article_110229_1b956d4221c8bddd51e2ed6d190e4f51.pdf

– Source 3 Description: (خالد بلعربي، الوضع في الجزائر متأخراً سقوط الدولة الزيانية (910 – 962 هـ / 1505 – 1554 م)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/8279>

– Source 1 Description: لطيفة بشاري بن عميرة، علاقة بني عبد الواد (بنو زيان، تلمسان) ببني مرين (المغرب) بين القرن 7 - 10هـ / 13م - 16م

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/131820>

– Source 2 Description: لطيفة بشاري، جهود يغمراسن بن زيان وابنه أبي سعيد عثمان في إقامة إمارة بني عبد الواد

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/111289>

– Source 3 Description: لطيفة بن عميرة، تلمسان من نشأتها إلى قيام دولة بني عبد الواد

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: تنافسي مع الدولة الحفصية في تونس والمربنية في المغرب

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: نظام ملكي وراثي

Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: في بعض الحالات في تعيين الأبناء كورثة للحكم

Assigned by class:

– Yes

Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: الملوك والحكام كانوا ذكور فقط

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

– Yes

Notes: فيه شروط لتولي الحكم متعلقة بالدين والأخلاق والسياسة وغيرها

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: القرابة العائلية

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: التوسع ونشر الاسلام

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: الفقهاء والعلماء كانوا مقربين من الحكام

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: كان هناك تعايش مع الديانات الأخرى ولكن المرتد عن الدين كان يعاقب بما نص عليه الشرع الاسلامي

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: الدولة الزيرية مجموعة دينية سنية في المغرب الأوسط تنتمي إلى المغرب الاسلامي

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: عرفت 7 حكام وأمراء بارزين منهم: 1- يغمراسن بن زيان بين 1236 و1283م 2- أبو سعيد عثمان بن يغمراسن بين 1283 و1303م. 3- أبو حمو موسى الأول بين 1308 و1318م. 4- عبد الرحمن ابن تاشفين بين 1318 و1337م. 5- أبو سعيد وابو الثابت بين 1348 و1354م 6- أبو حمو موسى الثاني بين 1359 و1389م 7- أبي عبد الله محمد المتوكل بين 1442 و1468م

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: القرآن

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: اللغة الشفهية الثانية في الدولة الزيانية كانت البربرية (الأمازيغية) وهذا لأصول السكان إلى جانب اللغة الرسمية والمكتوبة وهي العربية

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: الفقهاء في الاجتهاد والفقهاء وأصول الفقه والقياس

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: العلماء والفقهاء

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: كتاب القرآن والحديث النبوي

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: المساجد

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: المساجد

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: أماكن مقدسة لبعض الصلحاء والمتصوفة:

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: العمارة الزيانية والموحدية والمرابطية والمرينية والموريسكية

Notes: عرفت الدولة الزيانية العمارة الزيانية والموحدية والمرابطية والمرينية والموريسكية

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: الهلال والنجمة الخماسية

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: اليد بخمسة أصابع...

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: المساجد وبيوت العبادة

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: الحج الأكبر فقط

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: لمن استطاع للحج سبيلا

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: من صميم الدين والاسلام

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable items:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: الكفن

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: مقابر جماعية أو عائلية

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: رب السموات والأرض

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: مالك الملك وإليه يرجع كل شيء

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: الانسان بالعموم هو خليفة الله في الأرض

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: مالک الملک، الهادي، القادر، البصير، السميع، الكبير...

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: يعلم كل شيء وما تبدي نفس وما تكتم

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: يعلم كل شيء سره وظاهره والذي نعلم والذي لا نعلم

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: الحسنات والجنة

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: المرض، جهنم، السيئات...

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: رحمان، رحيم، غفور

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: جبار، متكبر، شديد العقاب

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: يمتلك كل شيء

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: هناك 99 اسم وصفة لله سبحانه وتعالى وهي ميزات له

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: 'في الصلاة هو تواصل روحي عبر التعبد والدعاء' أدعوني أستجب لكم

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: عبر الدعاء والاجابة

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

–Yes [specify]: المسلم تواصله مباشر مع الله ولكن النبي محمد صلى الله عليه وسلم هو شفيع المسلمين

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: يراها أهل التقوى والعرفان

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

Notes: مس الجن ووسوسة الشيطان
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: يعلم المسلم أنه إما يدخل الجنة أو جهنم بعد الموت والقيامة

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: الله عنده علم الساعة وما تكسب غدا ومتى تموت

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: من أطاع الله وعمل صالحا وكان مؤمنا عملا وقولا

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: النجاة من العذاب وجهنم تكونى بالايمان الكامل وشفاعة النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم ورحمة الله

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: المسلم يعلم الآخرة والفناء ويؤمن بالقضاء والقدر والمصير إلى الجنة أو النار

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: أعراف ثقافية وأخرى دينية اسلامية

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– I don't know

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– I don't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: شهر رمضان كركن ايماني من الأركان الخمسة للاسلام

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: الخمر ولحم الخنزير وما أهل به لغير الله والدم والميتة هي محرّمات

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

– Yes

Notes: يمكن اعتبار الجهاد في سبيل الله تضحية

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: زكاة المال والعشور

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: الزكاة، العشور، الصدقة المالية

To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: كل الانسانية يمكن التصدق عليها

Destroyed:

– I don't know

Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: الصلوات الخمس، الصوم، الحج، الدعوة إلى الخير، العمل الخيري

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: الدين الاسلامي يساوي الأخلاق وهي ركن أساسي وشرط المسلم ليكون مسلماً

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: الوضوء والامتناع عن زخرف الدنيا وقت الصلاة والخشوع أثناءها

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: الصلاة، الصوم...

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: الخمر حرام

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: الأخوة القلبية في الله "قال: قال رسول الله ﷺ: "مثل المؤمنين في توادهم وتراحمهم وتعاطفهم مثل الجسد إذا اشتكى منه عضو تداعى له سائر الجسد بالسهر والحمى"

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: أخي، صاحبي، عمي، عزيزي

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: يتكفل بحاجات المسلمين ما يعرف ببيت المسلمين وكذا الوقف الاسلامي

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: مؤسسة بيت المال ومؤسسة الوقف

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: تلبية حاجة المحتاجين من بيت مال المسلمين

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: المسنين والعجزة عند مسلمي الدولة الزيانية مكفول بهم من طرف الأبناء والأهل وإلا فإن ذلك يعتبر من عقود الوالدين

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: من خلال عائلات هؤلاء الكبار والعجزة

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: الذكور أكثر، لأن طبيعة هذه المجتمعات هي أبوية باطرارية

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: المدارس التابعة للدولة، والكتاتيب

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: عادة ما يكون منفصل بين الذكور والإناث في سن متقدمة

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: بيت المال يوفر المال والطعام

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: كل الخيرين في الدولة

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: النقل كان بالحيوانات والدواب والعربات ومستقل

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: الطرق

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: الخراج والعشور والزكاة والجزية

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: الضرائب والعشور على كل مالك يصله ماله لنصاب ذلك

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: كانت هناك قوات من الشرطة والجند والحرس

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: القصاص في حالة القتل مثلا

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: خارج المجموعة أو القبيلة

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: الجلد وقطع اليد وهي حدود السرقة والزنا وغيره وفي القصاص أيضا 'العين بالعين والسن بالسن والبادئ' 'أظلم'

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: نعم كانت هناك فئات المنيوزين من المساجين مثلا

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: حجز الأملاك لدفع الدية مثلا في حالة القتل أو في حالة دين غير مدفوع أو ضرائب غير مسددة

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: قانون مستخلص من الشريعة الاسلامية ويتطابق معها إلى جانب بعض الأعراف

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: الجند والحرس

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: (الجميع يتكلم اللغة العربية إلى جانب جزء يتكلم إلى جانبها اللغة البربرية (الأمازيغية)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: تقويم قمري وزراعي قديم

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: الطعام لجميع مسلمي الدولة ومجموعتها

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: 2009. الدولة الزبانية، حساني، مختار. تاريخ الدولة الزبانية، ج1، الأحوال السياسية. الجزائر: منشورات الحضارة، 2009.

Reference: 2009. الدولة الزبانية، حساني، مختار. تاريخ الدولة الزبانية، ج2. الجزائر: منشورات الحضارة، 2009.

Reference: - 1235 م / 681 هـ - 633 هـ دراسة الإدارة والحضارة 633 هـ - 681 هـ / 1235 م - 2011. الجزائر: منشورات المنهل، 2011.

Reference: 2023. الدولة الزبانية، كامل شاهين، فاتن. "دولة بنو عبد الواد (بنو زيان): دراسة تاريخية". العراق: مجلة الباحث، 2023.

Reference: "الحركة العلمية في حضرة تلمسان وعناية السلطة الزبانية بها ق. 8 - 9 هـ / 14 - 15 م"، 2018. <https://doi.org/10.33858/0500-000-019-054>.

